

LASER PULSE

PREVENTING/COUNTERING VIOLENT EXTREMISM MONITORING, EVALUATION, & LEARNING (MEL): CONTAINMENT/INTERDICTION

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About LASER PULSE

LASER (Long-term Assistance and Services for Research) PULSE (Partners for University-Led Solutions Engine) is a 10-year, \$70M program funded by USAID's Innovation, Technology, and Research Hub, that delivers research-driven solutions to field-sourced development challenges in USAID partner countries.

A consortium led by Purdue University, with core partners Catholic Relief Services, Indiana University, Makerere University, and the University of Notre Dame implements the LASER PULSE program through a growing network of 3,700+ researchers and development practitioners in 86 countries.

LASER PULSE collaborates with USAID missions, bureaus, and independent offices, and other local stakeholders to identify research needs for critical development challenges, and funds and strengthens the capacity of researcher-practitioner teams to co-design solutions that translate into policy and practice.

About the Armed Conflict and Violence Prevention Learning Agenda

The Conflict and Violence Prevention Learning Agenda Implementation Team (CVP LAIT) was tasked with co-creating and implementing a bureau-wide learning agenda that:

- Establishes the evidence base for effective approaches to armed conflict and violence prevention;
- Identifies opportunities for CVP investments that would produce new knowledge to fill gaps in the existing literature;
- Provides USAID staff with events, tools, resources, and/or guidance to incorporate learning agenda findings into their work; and
- Conducts original research into armed conflict and violence prevention.

Through an intensive, multi-stakeholder consultation process with USAID Washington and mission staff, P/CVE was identified as an effort that, if backed by sound evidence and guidance, could benefit program design, outcomes, policy, and knowledge generation.

Disclaimer

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ACRONYMS

AfP	Alliance for Peacebuilding
CI	Containment/Interdiction
CSO/s	Civil Society Organizations
CVE	Countering Violent Extremism
CVP LAIT	Conflict and Violence Prevention Learning Agenda Implementation Team
DDRR	Disengagement, Deradicalization, Rehabilitation, and Reintegration
LASER PULSE	Long-term Assistance and Services for Research Partners for University-Led Solutions Engine
MEL	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning
P/CVE	Preventing/Countering Violent Extremism
PI	Principal Investigator
PV	Prevention
PVE	Preventing Violent Extremism
ToC/s	Theory/ies of Change
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VE	Violent Extremism

RESEARCH SUMMARY

This research aims to better understand the current state of measurement with regard to containment/interdiction (CI) programming across the broader preventing/countering violent extremism (P/CVE) landscape. The following report explores the general characteristics of CI studies, including explicit indicators, common measurement trends, and indicator examples, to determine what CI programs are seeking to change. The studies analyzed for this research were curated from a P/CVE systematic mixed method review that contained 50 CI-related studies, of which 39 (78%) contained explicit indicators—the characteristics of these studies are synthesized within the body of this report.

In total, 679 indicators were extracted for analysis. Collectively, these measures depicted CI-oriented activities focused on increasing governmental capacity to prepare, report, and respond to any form of violent extremism (VE). These efforts often occur alongside efforts to increase police and security forces' capacity to detect, deter, and/or prosecute perpetrators of VE.

Findings from the CI studies reveal a broad spectrum of measures that resonate with varied themes, predominantly focused on measuring changes in attitudes and behaviors. The trends suggest the field is taking a comprehensive approach that not only counters extremist narratives, but also tries to build a robust, cohesive, and resilient community fabric. These indicators demonstrate that CI interventions are about countering VE, as well as fostering positive community dynamics, emphasizing collaboration, economic stability, and community trust.

Overall, the indicators encompass a broad spectrum of measures. From gauging the community's perception of safety and trust in governmental performance, to assessing changes in behavioral practices around gender equality and youth engagement, to understanding the quality of relationships within communities, the metrics span a broad spectrum. However, the spotlight on capacity-building dimensions, such as the strength of civil society and economic development, reveals the multi-layered efforts in ensuring communities are not only resilient, but also empowered.

This research lays a promising foundation on the measurement of CI programming, showcasing existing indicators and measures as examples of the current state of measurement, while highlighting the necessity for ongoing development and validation of theories of change (ToCs), indicators, and program approaches. While these examples serve as inspiration for creating contextualized and participatory monitoring and evaluation frameworks and can potentially contribute to establishing standard indicators for the P/CVE field, it is crucial to align them with the specific goals, outcomes, and local contexts of each program to ensure accurate and effective evaluation. Further, the current indicators and measures demonstrate that there still exists a gap between observed changes in attitudes, behaviors, and social networks and actual impacts in VE outcomes. To advance the field of P/CVE measurement, researchers and implementers need to establish clear correlations between intermediate changes and tangible VE results to better identify which interventions lead to meaningful reductions in VE. This approach ensures better allocation of resources and development of a stronger evidence base, enabling more targeted and effective interventions in future strategies.

INTRODUCTION

VE stands as one of the most significant security threats facing the international community, with the frequency of violent acts and atrocities perpetrated by extremists escalating across the world. Despite the looming threats and known impacts of VE, designing indicators and measuring change in P/CVE interventions is inherently complex due to their multifaceted nature. These programs operate within intricate socio-political landscapes, making direct attribution of outcomes to specific interventions challenging. While quantitative indicators might offer clarity, they often miss nuanced changes better

captured by qualitative measures. Establishing accurate baselines is also problematic, especially where data on VE is limited or unreliable. The fluidity of definitional boundaries in VE and its actual manifestation, combined with varying perceptions of success among stakeholders, further complicates consistent indicator development. Moreover, data collection poses both sensitivity and security risks, and tensions persistent between achieving measurable outcomes and making genuine—albeit less tangible—impacts. As such, creating universally accepted and effective indicators for P/CVE requires a nuanced, adaptable approach that respects the diverse and evolving contexts in which these programs operate.

Consequently, the actual impact of many interventions remains ambiguously documented, leaving the effectiveness of different approaches largely unassessed, especially in relation to VE goals. The overall absence of uniform indicators and measures to gauge intervention outcomes and participant change magnify other methodological and logistical challenges to P/CVE evaluation, hindering the field's ability to aggregate evidence and articulate what works. To address these deficiencies and build on the emerging base of P/CVE measurement, this research aims to better understand the current state of measurement with regard to CI programming. CVE interventions are an indispensable facet of a national security strategy, addressing the threat of radicalization once it has taken root, serving to both prevent and counter VE.

The following report explores the general characteristics of CI studies that include explicit indicators and measures and common measurement trends across CI indicators, including related examples, to determine what, exactly, CI programs are seeking to change.

MEL REPORT METHODOLOGY

To address deficiencies in assessment of P/CVE measurements and build on the nascent base of P/CVE measurement, this research complements an extensive systematic mixed method review of relevant P/CVE literature to extract, analyze, and curate P/CVE indicators and measures across three primary programming responses: (1) *prevention (PV)*; (2) *containment/Interdiction (CI)*; and (3) *disengagement, deradicalization, rehabilitation, and reintegration (DDRR)*.

Many of the included studies fell across multiple programming responses and ToCs, and even though all attempts were made by multiple researchers to separate them, the strong overlap of studies across programming responses and ToCs reflects the field's current programming and funding practice. While in theory there exist strong distinctions, this is not reflected in current practice. This suggests a critical need for more rigorous, specific, and nuanced methodologies in measuring and differentiating the impacts of various P/CVE interventions. Addressing this will enhance the effectiveness and specificity of P/CVE strategies, leading to more accurate assessments and improved outcomes.

An analysis of the research and existing literature led to a focus on exploring trends in measuring changes in attitudes, behaviors, relationship and social networks, and capacity building in evaluation of P/CVE programs. This report presents the findings from the review of CI interventions. A detailed description of this research methodology is available in the accompanying *P/CVE Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning: Methodology* report.

INCLUDED STUDIES

The finalized P/CVE systematic mixed method review contained 50 studies related to CI, of which 39 (78%) contained explicit indicators. In total, 679 indicators were extracted for further analysis, with an average of 17 indicators per CI study.

The studies employed a wide variety of program activities to achieve CI goals. Awareness raising and/or narrative creation

stood out as the primary focus. Such activities encompass the sharing of information and resources in various community settings to highlight warning signs, risk factors, and VE recruitment methodologies. Dialogue also featured prominently, facilitating safe conversations between government entities, civil service organizations (CSOs), and community members. Moreover, there was a noticeable emphasis on systemic capacity building activities, which entailed the formulation of strategic action plans to enhance service delivery by governments and specialized training for the prison and security sector. The studies also highlighted the significance of pro-social and cultural activities, spotlighting community exchanges, debates, sports competitions, and artistic events.

Understanding the context and methodological approach of studies with explicit CI indicators is crucial for understanding the current measurement landscape. A study’s context impacts the indicators’ applicability and universality, while its methodology speaks to the indicators’ reliability and validity. By examining these aspects, one gains insights into the strength of the evidence behind the indicators and their adaptability in the ever-evolving CI landscape. However, it is important to acknowledge that while these are best practices in theory, in practice, one often sees less consistency and encounters numerous methodological limitations. These challenges can significantly affect the interpretation and applicability of the findings. Ultimately, a deep-dive into these study characteristics provides a clearer picture of current CI measurements and paves the way for future advancements, helping to refine shared definitions of success. This section provides information related to the geographic context, types of studies, research methodology, and publication and evaluation timelines of the 39 CI studies that contained indicators.

Geographic Reach

CI research was conducted in 27 countries. Kenya, Somalia, and Kyrgyzstan emerged as the primary research locations, accounting for 34% of the studies, respectively. The number of countries may not match the number of resources, as some studies focus on the same or multiple countries. On a broader regional scale, East and West Africa led in research frequency, with Central Asia and Southeast Asia following suit.

Figure 1: Geographic spread of CI Research

Document Types

All included CI documents (100%) were organizational self-published programmatic evaluations.

Timeline Publication and Evaluation

The majority of CI studies were published in the last four years, with 59% (N=23) published between 2019 and 2022. Notably, 2019 witnessed the pinnacle of research publications at 24% (N=9), succeeded by 2021 (17%), and 2022 (12%), underlining the burgeoning interest in CI research.

Studies were also coded to determine the time elapsed between program implementation and evaluation. Notably, 41% (N=16) of included studies did not include substantial

Figure 2: Timeline of publication of CI studies

information on timeline of program implementation and/or timeline of evaluation conducted. Conversely, the most prevalent studies were *endline evaluations*,¹ reflecting 41% (N=16) of included resources, followed by *concurrent evaluations*² (15%, N=6) and *ex-post evaluations*³ (3%, N=1).

Methodology: Research Design, Evaluation, Analysis, and Limitations

The research design of CI studies is most commonly reported as mixed methods, reflecting 44% of included studies. The next most common research designs were multi-methods studies⁴ and qualitative studies (26% each), and randomized control trials and quantitative descriptive studies (3% each). There were no included CI studies that applied a non-randomized research design.

CI studies are most commonly reported as mixed or multi-methods research designs. Nearly all studies (90%) reported using more than one method of data collection. The most common type of data collection includes key informant interviews (81%), followed by enumerated and self-administered surveys (71%), and focus groups and document/desk review (63% each),

68% of the corpus reported examining the effect the intervention had on participants and whether these effects matched the objectives. A few studies (2%) also executed process evaluations, which focus on the actors that determine or influence the implementation of the program or project activities and provide insight into the changes that happen during them. The type of evaluation was undeterminable for 10% of CI studies.

Of studies reporting analysis methods (N=34), more than half of the studies (59%) reported using more than one method of data analysis. Of the types of analysis techniques used, 39% were quantitative in design, 46% were qualitative, and 14% were mixed-methods. The most prevalent methods of analyses are descriptive statistics (51% of studies), thematic analyses (33%), comparative analysis and ToC/hypothesis testing analysis (15% each), and contribution analysis (10%).

Research Design	N	%
Mixed Methods Studies	17	44%
Multi-Methods Studies	10	26%
Qualitative Studies	10	26%
Randomized Control Trial Studies	1	3%
Quantitative Descriptive Studies	1	3%
Non-Randomized Studies	0	0%

Table 1: Research design of CI studies

Analysis Methods	N	%
Descriptive Statistics	20	51%
Thematic Analyses	13	33%
Comparative Analysis	6	15%
Theory of Change/Hypothesis Testing Analysis	6	15%
No Analysis Mentioned	5	13%
Contribution Analysis	4	10%
Content and Discourse Analyses	3	8%
Regression Analyses	2	5%
Inferential Statistics	2	5%
Case Study and Ethnography	2	5%
Contextual Analysis	2	5%
Gender and Social Inclusion	2	5%
Economic Evaluations	1	3%
Network Analysis	1	3%
Time Series and Trends	1	3%
Action-Oriented Research	1	3%
Stakeholder and Social Media	1	3%
Most Significant Change/ Outcome Harvesting	1	3%
Process Tracing	1	3%

Table 2: Analysis methods of CI indicators

¹ Endline evaluation reflects evaluations conducted within the last three months of program implementation up to 1-year post program implementation.

² Concurrent evaluation reflects evaluations conducted at the same time as program implementation.

³ Ex-post evaluation reflects evaluations conducted greater than one-year post program implementation.

⁴ Multi-Methods Studies are studies that employed a combination of methods that did not meet the minimum criteria of social science research to be considered a Mixed Methods Study.

Study Limitation	Rank
Methodological Challenges and Limitations	1
Stakeholder Engagement and Cooperation Challenges	2
Logistical and Environmental Challenges	3
Security and Safety Concerns	4
Resource Constraints	5
Cultural and Societal Factors	6
Data Interpretation and Generalizability Challenges	7
Specific Regional and National Contexts	8
Project Adaptation or Change in Focus	9
Operational and Technical Challenges	10
Memory and Recall	11

Table 3: Ranked list of study limitations of CI resources

CI studies included in the analysis encountered a variety of limitations, with 85% reporting at least one explicit limitation within their evaluation. The most common reported limitations include methodological challenges, stakeholder engagement and cooperations, logistical and environmental challenges, and safety and security.

Of particular interest to monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL), methodological constraints included limitations related to lack of control groups, limited sample sizes, difficulties in attribution, heavy reliance on qualitative data, lack of baseline and endline data, and lack of generalizability of the findings. Challenges in stakeholder engagement also presented distinct limitations, including large number of refusals, inactive and unavailable stakeholders, low response rates particularly from women, and difficulty locating participants. Limitations in data interpretation and memory included concerns regarding the interpretation of findings

and the extent to which results can be generalized, alongside issues related to recall and social desirability biases.

CI INDICATORS AND MEASURES

CVE interventions are an indispensable facet of a national security strategy, addressing the threat of radicalization once it has taken root. As extremist ideologies evolve and manifest in various forms, governments must respond with a combination of legislative and security measures tailored to these challenges. These measures often include CI-oriented activities, which focus on increasing governmental capacity to prepare, report, and respond to any form of VE, and often occur alongside efforts to increase police and security forces' capacity to detect, deter, and/or prosecute perpetrators of VE. However, there are many different types of approaches to CI, reflecting different ToCs, target groups, analysis levels, and outcomes. To better understand current trends in measurement, the following section presents findings and related examples of current CI indicators and measures to determine what CI programs are seeking to change and at what level.

Disaggregates

More than half of the included studies (59%) explicitly present disaggregated information on at least one of the indicators used. In total, 229 of the coded indicators (34%) explicitly presented disaggregation, resulting in 10 discrete disaggregation themes. The most common type of indicator disaggregate is direct/indirect beneficiaries, followed by geographic location, gender, community members, and age.

Indicator Disaggregation	N	%
No Disaggregation Specified	450	66%
Direct/Indirect Beneficiaries	90	13%
Geographic Location	72	11%
Gender	53	8%
Community Members	34	5%
Age	31	5%
Time Series	23	3%
Intervention Type	20	3%
Stakeholders	15	2%
Sector	10	1%
Professional Role	9	1%
Ethnicity	7	1%
Other	6	1%

Table 4: Types of disaggregates of CI indicators

CI Recommendation:
Collect disaggregated data.

Given that only 59% of studies provided disaggregation of at least one indicator, there is still a great need to make this standard practice. More granular data, such as age, gender, or socio-economic background, can provide insights into which interventions work best for specific sub-groups.

Types of Change

P/CVE programs aim to effect change across multiple dimensions, from shaping attitudes, to altering behaviors, to increasing social networks, to building capacity generally. To develop a structure for analysis, this research analyzed and coded⁵ the 656⁶ indicators scraped from the CI studies across four distinct dimensions: attitudes, behaviors, relationships and social networks, and capacity building.

Usually, studies have indicators that span different types of change; only five CI studies had indicators that were coded within just one type of change, four of which only assessed attitudinal change, while one assessed behavioral change. Most commonly, CI studies have indicators assessing two or three types of change, with the most prevalent combination being attitudes and behaviors, followed by attitudes, behaviors, and relationships and social networks. The most common type of change being measured in CI programs is attitude change, followed closely by behavior change. There are only four studies in the CI corpus that do not include attitude-oriented indicators, and only eight studies that do not include behavior-oriented indicators.

Types of Change	N	%
Attitudes	300	46%
Behaviors	262	40%
Attitudes/Behaviors	7	1%
Relationships and Social Networks	50	8%
Behaviors/Relationships and Social Networks	1	0%
Capacity Building	36	5%

Table 5: Types of change of CI indicators

Indicator Levels

P/CVE programs encompass a multi-tiered approach to counter radicalization and VE. These tiers—spanning from individual factors, to community dynamics, to national and systemic issues—represent the levels of change a program aims to achieve and subsequently measure in their indicators. Together, these levels create a holistic P/CVE strategy, merging personal transformation, community resilience, and structural adjustments to tackle the complexities of VE. Within CI, over half (56%) of indicators measure change at the community (meso-level), 29% measure change at the individual (micro level), and only 16% measure change at the national (macro) level.

The following analysis of indicator themes, types of change, and their examples provides a sub-analysis of indicator levels across each.

⁵ Please reference the *Preventing/Countering Violent Extremism Monitoring, Evaluation, & Learning (MEL): Methodology* report for more explanation on the type of change analysis approach employed in this research.

⁶ A total of 23 indicators did not have enough information to assign a type of change and were hence excluded from this analysis.

Indicator Themes, Levels, and Examples

Themes were extracted through a thematic analysis⁷ of indicators across each of the four types of change, and results are presented below based on the type of change.

Attitudes

In the 307⁸ CI indicators that address changes in attitudes, 69 themes were developed. The table below presents more information on the most prevalent themes and their indicator level.

Table 6: Change in attitudes themes and indicator levels for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Attitudes	N	%	Individual (Micro)		Community (Meso)		National (Macro)	
			N	%	N	%	N	%
Perceived Level of Safety in Community	29	9%	13	46%	15	54%	0	0%
Gender Equality	21	7%	1	5%	18	86%	2	10%
Recidivism/Sentencing	19	6%	19	100%	0	0%	0	0%
Impact of Training	18	6%	14	78%	4	22%	0	0%
Perceptions of VE	17	6%	9	53%	8	47%	0	0%
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	17	6%	1	6%	16	94%	0	0%
Perceptions on Government Performance	17	6%	5	29%	12	71%	0	0%
Youth Engagement	13	4%	5	38%	8	62%	0	0%
Attitudes toward VE	29	9%	7	70%	3	30%	0	0%

Within the framework of CI measures in CVE programming, several thematic insights emerge concerning attitudinal change. The **perceived level of safety in the community**⁹ stands as a direct reflection of community confidence in security efforts, while **gender equality** illustrates the nuanced understanding of roles and rights across gender lines. **Recidivism/sentencing** offers a perspective into the perceived effectiveness of the justice system, whereas the **impact of training** gauges the efficacy of interventions. **Perceptions of VE** and **attitudes towards VE** delve into community sentiment towards VE, acting as barometers for prevailing views and potential vulnerabilities. The **capacity to address violence/conflict** underscores collective efficacy in addressing the root causes and manifestations of extremism. **Youth engagement** highlights the importance of harnessing the energy and perspectives of younger generations in CVE efforts. Finally, **perceptions on government performance** serve as a measure of public trust in the state's ability to handle extremism.

Attitude-related indicators were predominantly focused on changes at the individual and community level; however, they were reported across all three indicator levels. Attitudes assess changes occurring within the personal/psychological realm 41% of the time, within or between communities (including subgroups of a community) 55% of the time, and at the national or macro-level 4% of the time.

⁷ Please reference the *Preventing/Countering Violent Extremism Monitoring, Evaluation, & Learning (MEL): Methodology* report for more explanation on the thematic analysis approach employed in this research.

⁸ This includes indicators that assess both attitudes and behaviors.

⁹ Of the 29 indicators under perceived level of safety in community, only 28 were able to be thematically coded as either micro, meso, and/or macro. The remaining indicator did not have enough information to thematically code it.

Table 7: Indicator examples of attitudes change for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Attitudes	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Perceived Level of Safety in Community	Perception of threats	Q1. Do you feel more or less afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than you did a year ago?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I feel much more afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than I did a year ago • I feel somewhat more afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than I did a year ago • I don't feel more or less afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than I did a year ago • I feel somewhat less afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than I did a year ago • I feel much less afraid of being a victim of insurgents today than I did a year ago
Gender Equality	Attitudes on gender	<p>Q1. In your community, are women involved in traditional conflict resolution?</p> <p>Q2. If yes, how are women in your community involved in conflict resolution activities?</p>	<p>Refer to Q1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To a very great extent • To a great extent • Neither small nor great extent • To a small extent • To a very small extent • Not at all <p>Refer to Q2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being part of peace committee • Advising/counseling husbands • Advising youth • Other (specify)
Recidivism/Sentencing	Technical knowledge about the treatment of high-risk inmates	Q1. Knowledge about existing handling procedures of high risk inmates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Do not know
Impact of Training	Perception of impact of activities by beneficiaries/ participants	<p>Q1. Can you please describe the activities you were involved in through [insert activity name]?</p> <p>Q2. What is the best thing about [insert activity name]?</p>	Open ended

Themes: Changes in Attitudes	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Impact of Training (cont.)		<p>Q3. The intended aims of [insert activity name] were to [insert intended objectives of the activity]. To what extent do you think that [insert activity name] achieved these intended objectives?</p> <p>Q4. [If respondents reply positively to Q3] What were the critical factors that helped [insert grantee name] achieve this success?</p> <p>Q5. [If respondents reply negatively to Q3] What were the critical factors that hindered [insert grantee name] success? How could [insert grantee name] have achieved more success?</p>	
Perceptions of VE	Personal perception toward violent extremism and peace narratives	Q1. Under what condition(s) do you think it is justified to engage in violence? You can choose more than one.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When myself or my family is insulted or threatened • When my belief or religion is insulted or threatened • When my ethnic background is insulted or threatened • When my ideology or political choice is insulted or threatened • When my voice is unheard • When my livelihood is threatened • Others, please fill the blank
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	Perception of changes in capabilities around opportunities to talk to peers about ways to prevent violence and extremist attitudes	<p>As a result of the project, please rate the following statements:</p> <p>Q1. I have had opportunities to talk to my peers about ways to prevent violence and extremist attitudes</p>	<p>For Q1-Q3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree • Not applicable

Themes: Changes in Attitudes	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict (cont.)		<p>Q2. (If agrees) I believe that this change will persist in the near future (over the coming year)</p> <p>Q3. (If agrees) I believe that change will persist long-term (beyond the coming year)</p>	
Perceptions of Government Performance	Perceptions of the performance of state government	<p>Q1. I am going to read out a number of issues the government is currently working to address. Please tell me if you think the federal government is doing a very good job (= 1), somewhat good job (= 2), neither good nor bad job (= 3), somewhat bad job (= 4), or very bad job (= 5) to address the following issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic services like water and electricity • Security • Unemployment • Government corruption • Decent wages and salaries • Education • Healthcare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A very good job • Somewhat good job • Neither good nor bad job • Somewhat bad job • Very bad job
Youth Engagement	Percentage of targeted youth with improved perceptions of government	<p>Rate your agreement to the following statement:</p> <p>“The government will surely listen and respond if the out-of-school youth ask their help when they are not treated fairly by others.”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't know • I strongly disagree • I disagree • I somewhat disagree • I somewhat agree • I agree • I strongly agree
Attitudes Toward VE	Confidence in non-violent means of change	<p>Q1. Have you attended a lawful/peaceful demonstration or protest march?</p> <p>Q2. Do you think this is an effective way to get improvements in your area?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No

Behaviors

In the 270¹⁰ CI indicators that address changes in behaviors, 60 themes were developed. The table below presents more information on the most prevalent themes and their indicator level.

Table 8: Change in behaviors themes and indicator levels for CI indicators

Themes: Change in Behaviors	N	%	Individual (Micro)		Community (Meso)		National (Macro)	
			N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender Equality	31	11%	0	0%	26	84%	5	16%
Youth Engagement	30	11%	9	32%	18	64%	1	4%
Strength of Civil Society (Capacity)	19	7%	3	16%	8	42%	8	42%
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	18	7%	0	0%	16	89%	2	11%
Youth Development	14	5%	2	14%	9	64%	3	21%
Strength of Civic Knowledge	9	3%	2	22%	1	11%	6	67%
Judicial Capacity	8	3%	0	0%	3	38%	5	63%
Legal/Judicial Capacity Building	7	3%	0	0%	6	86%	1	14%

In the context of CI measures within CVE programming, assessing behavioral changes offers a multi-dimensional understanding through several thematic avenues. **Gender equality** serves not only as an attitudinal marker, but also as a behavioral indicator, observing shifts in practices and participation across gender lines. **Youth engagement**¹¹ emphasizes the active involvement of young individuals in peacebuilding and CVE initiatives, a testament to their role as proactive agents of change. The **strength of civil society (capacity)** and **capacity to address violence/conflict** are intertwined, indicating the proactive actions of civil bodies and their tangible contributions towards mitigating extremism. **Youth development** is a broader gauge of how the younger generation is being nurtured and involved in shaping safer communities. **Strength of civic knowledge** mirrors active community engagement in democratic processes and understanding of civic rights and responsibilities. **Judicial capacity** and **legal/judicial capacity building** delve deeper into the justice system, spotlighting both the responsiveness of the judiciary and the efforts to fortify its infrastructure against VE challenges.

Behavior-related indicators were predominantly focused on changes at the community and individual level; however, they were reported across all three indicator levels. Behavioral changes occurred within the personal/psychological realm 18% of the time, within or between communities (including subgroups of a community) 56% of the time, and at the national or macro-level 26% of the time.

¹⁰ This includes indicators that assess behaviors and attitudes, as well as behaviors and relationships and social networks.

¹¹ Of the 30 indicators under youth engagement, only 28 were able to be thematically coded as either micro, meso, and/or macro. The remaining two indicators did not have enough information to thematically code it.

Table 9: Indicator examples of behaviors change for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Behaviors	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Gender Equality	Inclusive programming (gender)	# of listeners to media campaigns promoting female historic figures from minority backgrounds	Count
Youth Engagement	# of targeted youth who regularly communicate on and participate in coordination and advocacy meetings on peace and security issues at the local level.	Q1. Have you (youth) participated in any meetings (especially with county governments) to help influence policies/laws on peace and security?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know/cannot remember
Strength of Civil Society (Capacity)	Enhanced citizen engagement	Total # of civil society organizations adding a PVE or digital literacy element to existing programming, with support of XXX training or information materials	Count
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	Extent to which XXX Committees are used for addressing and resolving conflicts	Q1. Community dialogue and planning with local officials have helped make this settlement a better place to live.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Somewhat agree • Somewhat disagree • Strongly disagree
Youth Development	% of participants capacitated in advocacy and communication who participate in political decision -processes that directly affect groups of most at-risk youth	<p>Please rate the following statements, based on your experience participating in different activities of the project:</p> <p>Q1. I thought the XXX training sessions were very well tailored to the needs of youth in my town/village.</p> <p>Q2. I learned new things at the XXX training that were not taught to me anywhere else before.</p> <p>Q3. I learned to speak effectively in front of an audience thanks to the XXX training.</p>	<p>For Q1-Q5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Agree • Neutral • Disagree • Strongly disagree • Not applicable

Themes: Changes in Behaviors	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Youth Development (cont.)		<p>Q4. I still use some of the skills and knowledge I gained through the XXX training.</p> <p>Q5. Girls and boys had equal opportunities to be actively engaged in the training sessions.</p>	
Strength of Civic Knowledge	Dissemination of skills and knowledge	With whom have you shared your new skills and knowledge?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family members • Colleagues in my organization • Community members • Friends/school mates • Community leaders • Colleagues at other • Organizations • Colleagues in my local government • People from my mosque/ church • Business partner • I have not shared the information • Other
Judicial Capacity	# of courts piloting improved court administration and management procedures	Count	Count
Legal/Judicial Capacity Building	Increased knowledge among judges about judicial decision writing	# of trainees trained to conduct independent trainings for judges.	Count

Relationships and Social Networks

In the 51 CI indicators that measure social networks, 20 themes were developed. The table below presents more information on the most prevalent themes and their indicator level.

Table 10: Change in relationships and social networks themes and indicator levels for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Relationships and Social Networks	N	%	Individual (Micro)		Community (Meso)		National (Macro)	
			N	%	N	%	N	%
Integration	7	14%	1	14%	0	0%	6	86%
Social Cohesion	5	10%	0	0%	5	100%	0	0%
Quality of Relationship between Groups	5	10%	0	0%	5	100%	0	0%
Collaboration between Stakeholders	4	8%	1	25%	2	50%	1	25%
Youth Engagement	4	8%	0	0%	4	100%	0	0%
Personal Relationships with VEO	3	6%	1	33%	1	33%	1	33%
Perception of Trust or Lack Thereof within Their Neighborhood	3	6%	3	100%	0	0%	0	0%

In the realm of CI, assessing changes in relationships and social networks surfaces distinct themes. **Integration** emphasizes the assimilation of individuals into broader societal contexts, revealing how well diverse groups coalesce and share mutual aspirations. **Social cohesion** serves as a temperature gauge, measuring the strength of communal bonds and mutual respect. The **quality of relationship between groups** further dissects the harmony or discord between different societal segments, unveiling the depth of understanding and mutual appreciation. **Collaboration between stakeholders** showcases the concerted efforts among different entities, highlighting collective pursuits against extremist threats. The theme of **youth engagement** underlines the significance of young individuals as active participants and bridge-builders in knitting together different societal elements. **Personal relationships** offers a glimpse into the lingering affiliations with extremist elements, potentially either as vulnerabilities or opportunities for intervention. Lastly, **perception of trust or lack thereof within their neighborhood** serves as a barometer for localized faith and confidence, critical in any effort to fortify communities against extremist influences.

Relational-related indicators were predominantly focused on changes at the community, individual, and national level. Social network or relational changes occurred within the personal/psychological realm 24% of the time, within or between communities (including subgroups of a community) 55% of the time, and at the national or macro-level 22% of the time.

Table 11: Indicator examples of relationships and social networks change for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Relationships and Social Networks	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Integration	Social isolation	I feel isolated and excluded from my community most of the time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly agree • Somewhat agree • Somewhat disagree • Strongly disagree
Social Cohesion	Social inclusiveness in the community	Q1. Respondents were presented with the following statement: "I tell my children (or I will tell my future children) they should only marry people from the same ethnic group as theirs."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree • Neither • Disagree
Quality of Relationships Between Groups	Interaction across ethnic lines	Q1. Would you allow people from other ethnic groups settled in your ancestral land to belong to other political parties other than the one preferred by your ethnic group?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Undecided
Collaboration between Stakeholders	% of key state and non-state actors feel that collaboration on sharing of best practices of prevention of violent extremism between CA Central Asian countries increased	<p>Q1. In the last 2 years, to what extent do you think the collaboration on sharing best practices for preventing violent extremism (PVE) between CA countries increased?</p> <p>Q2. To what extent was/were the conference(s) organized by Search for Common Ground (SFCG) helpful for sharing experiences?</p> <p>Q3. To what extent did conference(s) facilitate the exchange of best practices and experience for the prevention of violent extremism between Central Asian countries?</p> <p>Q4. To what extent did the conference(s) increase collaboration between Central Asian countries?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To a moderate extent • To a great extent

Themes: Changes in Relationships and Social Networks			
Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples	
Collaboration between Stakeholders (cont.)		<p>Q5.To what extent did the conference(s) help you to establish/strengthen the connection with other Central Asian partners?</p> <p>Q6. Has the knowledge gained at the conference had an impact on your work?</p>	
Youth Engagement	# of roundtables between youth and community stakeholders	Frequency of round-tables between youth and community stakeholders (schools, families, juvenile police, and local government) on identified grievances/issues of most-at-risk youth	Count
Perception of Trust or Lack Thereof Within Their Neighborhood	Increased trust and cooperation between state institutions and religious organizations/communities	Q1.What do you think the level of trust between government institutions and religious organizations/communities will be after the project is completed?	Lack of trust scale from 1-10, with 10 being high confidence
Personal Relationships	% of people surveyed in the target communities in two countries having personal relationships with labour migrants and their families	Not available	Not available

Capacity Building

In the 26 CI indicators that measure capacity, 15 themes were developed. The table below presents more information on the most prevalent themes and their indicator level.

Table 12: Change in capacity building themes and indicator levels for CI indicators

Themes: Change in Capacity Building	N	%	Individual (Micro)		Community (Meso)		National (Macro)	
			N	%	N	%	N	%
Strength of Civil Society (Capacity)	8	22%	1	14%	5	71%	1	14%
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	8	22%	0	0%	5	63%	3	38%
Legal/Judicial Capacity Building	3	8%	0	0%	3	100%	0	0%
Economic Development	2	6%	0	0%	2	100%	0	0%
Citizen Access to Services	2	6%	1	50%	0	0%	1	50%

Within CI measurements, focusing on capacity building unveils a set of vital dimensions. **Strength of civil society (capacity)**¹² signifies the robustness of community-based organizations, showcasing how well civil society can shape, influence, and advocate for broader societal concerns. **Capacity to address violence/conflict** gauges the readiness and effectiveness of formal and informal entities in mitigating and resolving conflicts, serving as a litmus test for proactive and reactive measures. **Legal/judicial capacity building** underlines the importance of a competent and fair judicial framework, reflecting efforts to ensure that justice is served and perceived as equitable. **Economic development** broadens the scope to the tangible livelihoods and financial growth of communities, suggesting that a thriving economy can be a buffer against extremist influences. Lastly, **citizen access to services** assesses the ease and equality with which individuals can access public goods and services, symbolizing the inclusiveness and efficiency of governance structures.

Capacity building related indicators were predominantly focused on changes at the community and national level; however, they were reported across all three indicator levels. Capacity changes occur within the personal/psychological realm 15%, within or between communities (including subgroups of a community) 64% of the time, and at the national or macro-level 21% of the time.

Table 13: Indicator examples of capacity building change for CI indicators

Themes: Changes in Capacity Building	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Strength of Civil Society (Capacity)	# of organizations adding a PVE element to existing programming as a result of training	Count	Count
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict	Impact of project	Q1. What project activities or approaches were most effective in securing positive outcomes and why?	Select all options that apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 = Community dialogue 2 = Capacity building sessions

¹² Of the eight indicators under strength of civil society (capacity), only seven were able to be thematically coded as either micro, meso, and/or macro. The remaining indicator did not have enough information to thematically code it.

Themes: Changes in Capacity Building	Indicator Examples	Measure Examples	Measure Option Examples
Capacity to Address Violence/Conflict (cont.)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 = Government led initiatives • 4 = CSO led initiatives • 5 = Community led initiatives • 6 = Others
Legal/Judicial Capacity Building	# of capacitated select law enforcement individuals ... who provide social protection support and assistance.	# of internal affairs officers engaged in community policing work	Count
Economic Development	Opportunities for economic growth	QI. Thinking about your economic and financial status now compared with two years ago, would you say you are better off, worse off, or about the same?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better off now compared with two years ago • Worse off now than two years ago • About the same as two years ago • Refused to answer
Citizen Access to Services	Service delivery by local governments improved	QI. How can government social services be improved to help vulnerable youth group?	Open ended

Indicator Themes and Example Recommendations

Expand measures for evaluating training impacts.

Given the emphasis on education in CI, ensure that training indicators and measures are not only about content delivery, but also transformative thinking, critical evaluation, and ideological resilience.

Prioritize longitudinal studies.

The impact of CI programs on ideological shifts might not be immediate. Invest in longitudinal studies that track changes over extended periods to gauge the sustained impact of interventions.

Diversify ideological assessment.

Given the varied nature of extremist ideologies, CI programs should capture a broader spectrum of ideological beliefs. This expansion ensures that the diverse nuances and layers of extremist thought are adequately addressed.

Incorporate indicators related to technology.

Given the rise of online radicalization, incorporate metrics that track digital engagements, online discourse trends, and shifts in the digital landscape of extremist content.

Level of Indicators and Interventions

CI programs and their subsequent measures encompass a multi-level approach to counter radicalization and VE and address the threat of radicalization once it has taken root. However, there can frequently be a disconnect between the intervention level and what a program is actually measuring based on their indicators. For instance, a program designed to improve whole-of-government capacity to analyze and respond to the drivers of VE through local engagement may only assess individual skills or knowledge acquisition—change at the individual level. This incongruity between the change a program is designed to impact and what it is actually assessing may lead to misleading interpretations by underestimating or overestimating a program's impact.

To assess alignment between level of indicators and their interventions as a proxy of indicator validity, studies were coded on whether their intended intervention level matched their indicator levels. Studies could either mismatch, match, or exceed the change the program originally intended to achieve. Matches denote that the level of measurement—of at least one indicator¹³—matches or exceeds the level of intervention. Mismatch-Less Than implies

Indicator VS Intervention Level	N	%
Match	13	34%
Mismatch-Exceed	15	39%
Mismatch-Less Than	10	26%

Table 14: Level of indicator compared to intervention for CI

¹³ It is important to note that program outcomes and impact should not be measured exclusively by one indicator only, so these analyses are a way to identify potential incongruities or misinterpretations that could under/overestimate a program's impact and lead to questionable indicator validity.

that the indicators presented measured change at a level less than the intervention (i.e., indicators were focused on change at the individual level, but the reported goal/outcomes of the intervention were focused on change at the community level). Finally, Mismatch-Exceed implies that the indicators presented measured change a level greater than the intervention's reported goal/outcomes (i.e., indicators were attempting to measure or explore the impact of the intervention on higher-order outcomes).

The intersection of the intervention and indicator levels was examined across all CI indicators. The majority (73%) of CI studies had indicators that matched or exceeded their level of intervention. Of the 10 mismatching studies, six had indicators that measured change at the micro level, but four of the interventions aimed to affect change at the meso-level and two at the macro level. The remaining four studies had indicators that measured change at the meso-level, but aimed to affect change at the macro-level per their intervention. These findings suggest that there is a significant disconnect or misalignment between the stated objectives and the actual evaluation practices within 23% of the sample. This incongruity suggests that interventions may not be effectively capturing or demonstrating their true impact on the broader community, potentially leading to misinformed decision-making and reduced overall effectiveness of the interventions.

The fact that 73% of CI studies demonstrate a keen alignment between their indicators and intervention levels is demonstrative of the field's commitment to more rigorous evaluation. Such precise alignment ensures the true value and impact of interventions are captured and adequately represented. On the other hand, the misalignment observed in 23% of the sample is a pressing concern. Specifically, among these mismatching studies, there is a risk of understating the broader community or systemic impacts when interventions with meso- or macro-objectives are assessed with micro-level indicators. Similarly, those that measure at the meso-level, but target macro changes, may miss out on significant policy or national shifts. Such discrepancies could lead to potential misinterpretations of results, misinformed decision-making, and, subsequently, a diminished overall impact. Decision-makers and implementers must be conscious of this misalignment to ensure their evaluation strategies genuinely reflect their interventions' depth and breadth.

CI Recommendation:

Ensure alignment between indicators and intervention levels.

Given the substantial alignment of indicators and intervention levels in 73% of CI studies, it is crucial to maintain this rigorous approach across all studies. Aim for meticulous alignment across studies to accurately capture and represent the impact of interventions. Address the misalignment seen in 23% of studies by training practitioners and refining evaluation strategies, ensuring that the depth and breadth of interventions at all levels—a from micro to macro—are properly assessed and understood. This reduces the risk of misinterpretation, enhances decision-making, and ensures the maximum impact of P/CVE efforts.

CONCLUSION

CVE interventions, as crucial components of national security strategies, tackle the menace of radicalization head-on, ensuring societies remain resilient to the allure of extremist ideologies. The evolving landscape of extremism requires governments to be adaptive, marrying legislative finesse with robust security measures. CI-focused interventions specifically seek to enhance governmental readiness and responsiveness to varying VE threats and bridge gaps in police and security forces' capabilities to detect and respond.

This research effort explores the general characteristics of CI studies that include explicit indicators, measures, and common measurement trends across CI indicators, including related examples, to better understand what CI programs are currently seeking to change. It is limited to the extent that evaluations publish and explicitly share this information, a practice that is still not common across the field. As such, it is possible that valuable resources may have been missed, leading to conclusions being drawn on partial data.

Understanding the specific themes across the different types of change provides insights into the nuanced approach of CI interventions. Within attitudes, CI interventions monitor public trust through indicators like *perceived level of safety* and *perceptions on government performance*, indicating community confidence in security and governance. The inclusion of *gender equality* highlights the evolving societal perspectives on gender roles, while *recidivism/sentencing* gauges trust in the justice system's fairness and ability to deter crime. Within behaviors, indicators such as *youth engagement* and *strength of civic knowledge* underscore active societal participation, emphasizing the roles of informed communities and proactive youth in CVE. The focus on *judicial capacity* and *legal/judicial capacity building* reveals the judicial system's preparedness and adaptability in the face of VE challenges. Within network and relationships, indicators like *integration*, *social cohesion*, and *quality of relationship* between groups serve as barometers for societal harmony, hinting at community vulnerabilities or strengths. Themes such as *collaboration between stakeholders* spotlight collective anti-VE efforts, while *personal relationships* identifies potential extremist affiliations and associated intervention points. Finally, within capacity building, the *strength of civil society (capacity)* theme emphasizes the significant role of grassroots organizations in shaping counter-/alternative narratives. Indicators like *capacity to address violence/conflict* offer insights into conflict resolution abilities, while *economic development* and *citizen access to services* respectively underscore the importance of economic stability and efficient governance in CVE initiatives.

A promising observation within measurement of CI programming is that a significant portion of CI studies ensures their objectives are mirrored in their measures. This alignment is a testament to the evolving maturity in the field of CVE programming, reflecting a commitment to impactful and insightful interventions. However, the existing incongruence, where the depth and breadth of interventions are not accurately captured, poses a risk of misinterpretation, potentially steering future strategies based on skewed insights. It is imperative that such misalignments are addressed, ensuring that evaluations genuinely and holistically capture the intended and unintended effects and impacts of the programs. While strides have been made in the right direction, an ever-present need for introspection, refinement, and precision in both implementation and evaluation of CI programming remains.

The findings presented herein lay a promising foundation on the state of measurement of CI programming; however, much work still needs to be done as the field continues to mature and develop tested and validated ToCs and programming approaches. This research effort serves as a beginning effort to look across the field of CI indicators and measures and understand how programs are defining, measuring, and testing different outcomes in PVE. The indicators, measures, and major themes presented in this research are meant to serve as examples of the current state of measurement and should not be taken as a recommendation for their use across all CI programs. Program indicators and measures should be developed to align with specific program goals and outcomes that are informed by the unique local and lived reality of the context in which a program will occur. However, these examples can serve as inspiration when designing new program monitoring

and evaluation frameworks and creating indicators to better refine and contextualize indicators, measures, and tools for each specific program. They can further act as a starting point to define and test a set of core standard indicators for the P/CVE field that could serve as a foundational framework to ensure consistent evaluation criteria across different programs and contexts and help advance the field towards aggregating results and studying collective impact of P/CVE programming.

P/CVE FIELD-BASED MEL RECOMMENDATIONS

Unique recommendations resulting from the CI findings presented within this report are incorporated within the report sections. The following overarching recommendations were informed by individual study recommendations, challenges, and best practices, as well as broader insights from research to enhance the state of P/CVE monitoring, evaluation, and learning. Some recommendations have been made by the researchers based on their subject-matter expertise.

- 1. Develop and test new indicators:** As the field of P/CVE measurement matures, it is crucial to develop and test new indicators across a variety of contexts. Existing indicators should not simply be copied and repeated in a cookie-cutter fashion.
- 2. Explore indicators and measures from other sectors:** To strengthen the robustness of VE programming metrics, it is essential to look beyond the P/CVE sector. Incorporating tested indicators and methodologies from fields like public health, education, and psychology can offer innovative perspectives and tools. These cross-sectoral approaches might reveal unexplored avenues to evaluate program effectiveness and impact, ensuring a more holistic assessment and increasing the potential for interdisciplinary collaboration.
- 3. Develop appropriate time-bound indicators:** Recognizing that many changes that interventions seek to achieve, such as improved trust, social cohesion, etc., take considerable time to affect and are often influenced by external factors outside the control of a program, it is vital that indicators be aligned with realistic expectations for change. It is crucial to ensure that indicators both capture achievable and realistic changes within an intervention timeframe and lay a foundation for capturing the nuances of long-term change contributing to broader phenomena like developing resilience and social cohesion.
- 4. Connect changes in attitudes, behaviors, social networks, and capacity building to VE outcomes:** It is essential to bridge the gap between observed changes in attitudes, behaviors, and social networks and actual impacts in VE outcomes. By establishing clear correlations between these intermediate changes and tangible VE results, programs can better identify which interventions lead to meaningful reductions in VE. This approach ensures a more precise allocation of resources and enables more targeted and effective interventions in future strategies. However, to effectively test the association between intermediate changes and long-term P/CVE outcomes, P/CVE programs must develop explicit ToCs and approaches that stabilize their interventions, ensuring more consistent intermediate changes and sustained long-term impacts.
- 5. Contextualize indicators:** Given the diversity in regions where P/CVE programs are implemented, it is critical to tailor indicators and measures to be culturally sensitive. Recognizing the local dynamics ensures a more accurate measurement of how ideologies take root and how they can be effectively countered. A comprehensive approach that incorporates diverse indicators addressing various ethnic, religious, socio-economic, and political dimensions is essential for a thorough assessment of the multifaceted factors influencing VE. This ensures that P/CVE measurements are not only contextually relevant, but also resonate with the specific push and pull factors, cultural, and social dynamics of each region.

- 6. Develop and test core standard indicators:** Following the contextualization of indicators, the next step is to develop a degree of standardization in measurement across the P/CVE field. Whilst recognizing the dynamic and unique nature of different contexts in which P/CVE programs operate, there is still an imperative need to introduce a degree of standardization in measurement. The P/CVE field should collaborate to identify, develop, and rigorously test a set of core standard indicators. These metrics would serve as a foundational framework to ensure consistent evaluation criteria across different programs and geographies, promoting comparability and cross-referencing. This process of standardization, balanced with the need for contextualization, sets a quality benchmark for all P/CVE initiatives, ensuring both broad applicability and local relevance in P/CVE measurements.
- 7. Develop and integrate quantitative and qualitative measures:** To gain a comprehensive understanding of VE programming impacts, it is crucial to blend the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. While quantitative metrics deliver concrete data points and trends, qualitative research delves into the nuanced lived experiences and perceptions of community members. By seamlessly integrating findings from both approaches, evaluations can capture the full spectrum of program outcomes – from tangible results to subtle shifts in beliefs and attitudes. This holistic view is instrumental in refining and enhancing the effectiveness of VE interventions.
- 8. Engage diverse stakeholders in indicator design:** Engage a wider range of stakeholders in measurement design, including religious leaders, educators, community elders, and even former extremists. Their insights can refine indicators, making them more relevant and actionable.
- 9. Promote community feedback mechanisms:** Create platforms where program beneficiaries/participants and community members can give feedback on P/CVE programs. Their on-the-ground insights can identify gaps, potential pitfalls, or areas of improvement.
- 10. Regularly update/refine indicators and reporting mechanisms:** Ideologies evolve, and so should the indicators. Regularly review and update measurement tools to remain current and address emerging trends in extremist thought. Develop real-time monitoring systems and feedback loops that allow program implementers to make timely adjustments based on emerging trends and findings.
- 11. Fund capacity building for local research:** Invest in training local researchers and institutions to develop, test, and collect P/CVE measurements. This not only builds local expertise, but also ensures that measurements are grounded in local realities.
- 12. Promote cross-program comparisons:** Encourage initiatives that allow for cross-comparison of P/CVE programs across different regions or countries. Such efforts can lead to best practice sharing and global collaboration.

By implementing these recommendations, the field of P/CVE programming can ensure more accurate, relevant, and actionable insights, driving more effective interventions tailored to the unique needs of each context.

CONTAINMENT/INTERDICTION PUBLICLY AVAILABLE INCLUDED STUDIES WITH INDICATORS

Citation	Research Design	Location
Amadou, Moussa A., Alliou Traoré, and Nina Taka. <i>Lafia (People at Peace): Endline Report</i> . United State Agency for International Development, 2021. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00Z621.pdf .	Multi-methods	Mali
Bean, Sharon, Patty Hill, Joseph Sany, and Susanne Riveles. <i>USAID/West Africa Peace through Development (PDEV)</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2011. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PDACR829.pdf .	Qualitative	Niger, Chad and Mauritania
<i>BFRP Est Region Cluster</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2021. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00Z5K8.pdf .	Multi-methods	Burkina Faso
Bilali, Rezarta. "Voices For Peace" <i>Impact Evaluation of a Radio Drama To Counteract Violent Extremism in The Sahel Region in Burkina Faso</i> , 2019. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/pa00w4g3.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Burkina Faso
Botoeva, Aisalkyn, Omar Salem, and Shiva K. Dhungana. <i>#JashStan: Supporting the Next Wave of Youth Peace Leaders in Kyrgyzstan</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2021. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Jashstan_Final_Report_Aug-31_2021.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kyrgyzstan
Cook, Gayla, and Abdi Younis. <i>Somalia Youth Livelihoods Program Final Evaluation</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2012. https://www.careevaluations.org/wp-content/uploads/evaluations/somali-youth-livelihoods-program.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Somalia
<i>Countering and Preventing Radicalization in Indonesian Prisons</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2011. https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5db70e83fc0a966cf4cc42ea/t/6585a38ea561a8791b6ca425/1703256974374/494.pdf .	Multi-methods	Indonesia
Della-Giacoma, Jim, and Shikhty Sunny. <i>Final Evaluation of Partnership for a Tolerant, Inclusive Bangladesh (PTIB) Project</i> . United Nations Development Program/NDP Independent Evaluation Office, 2021. https://erc.undp.org/evaluation/evaluations/detail/12625 .	Qualitative	Bangladesh
Ekesa, Obando, Bob Kanyi, and Japheth Ogola. <i>Inuka! Supporting Vulnerable Youth to Participate in Community Peace and Security Efforts in Coastal Kenya—End of Project Evaluation</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2021. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/SFCG_Kenya_FinalEvaluationReport_v1.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kenya
Emenogu, Augustus. <i>Final External Evaluation of the Deepening Peace in the Niger-Delta Program (Final Report)</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2020. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Final_External_Evaluation_of_The_Deepening_Peace_in_the_Niger-Delta_Program_Final-Report_ACEv3_28122020.pdf .	Qualitative	Nigeria
<i>Enhancing Efforts to Prevent Violent Extremism by Leveraging Behavioural Insights: Lessons Learned from Practical Experiments</i> . United Nations Development Programme, 2022. https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2022-03/UNDP-Enhancing-Efforts-to-Prevent-Violent-Extremism-by-Leveraging-Behavioural-Insights.pdf .	Quantitative randomized controlled trials	Uzbekistan, Pakistan, Tajikistan

Finkel, Steven E., Chris A. Belasco, Christian Gineste, Michael Neureiter, and John McCauley. <i>Peace Through Development II: Burkina Faso, Chad, and Niger</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2018. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00SVPK.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Burkina Faso, Chad, Niger
Gjoni, Roland, Nazgul Yergali, and Alfira Senkina. <i>Final Performance Evaluation of Kazakhstan Judicial Program (KJP)</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2020. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00WGCV.pdf .	Multi-methods	Kazakhstan
Hiariej, Eric, Ayu Diasti Rachmawati, Agustinus Moruk Taek, Mutiara Kurniasari, and Rizky Alif Alvian. <i>Reducing the Recruitment and Recidivism of Violent Extremists in Indonesia</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2017. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/INA029_DOS_BC_external_Evaluation_Report_FINAL_2017.pdf .	Multi-methods	Indonesia
Jailobaev, Temirlan, Kanykey Jailobaeva, Gulsaadat Baialieva, Gulnara Asilbekova, and Zeinep Eshmuratova. <i>Final Evaluation for the “Prevention of Violent Extremism in Central Asian Countries Through Strengthening Social Cohesion Among Labour Migrants, Returnees, and Their Families” Project</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2022. https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5db70e83fc0a966cf4cc42ea/t/6585ad7357de5a52c0230491/1703259508463/1464.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan
Jailobaeva, Kanykev, and Gulnara Asilbekova. <i>Social Media for Deradicalization in Kyrgyzstan: A Model for Central Asia</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2017. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/KGZ007_Evaluation_Report_Final_Nov_2017.pdf .	Qualitative	Kyrgyzstan
Jrad, Eya. <i>Promoting Civilian Engagement in Security Sector Reform Processes in Tunisia</i> . Search for Common Ground/Al-Kawakibi Democracy Transition Center, 2018. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Midterm_Eval_SSR_29_08.pdf .	Multi-methods	Tunisia
Khalil, James, and Oren Ipp. <i>Mali Transition Initiative: Final Evaluation</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2016. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/pa00m34d.pdf .	Qualitative	Mali
Kollmorgen, Jean-Camille, Mikewa Ogada, Selline Korir, and Elizabeth Dena. <i>Strengthening Community Resilience Against Extremism (SCORE) Mid-Term Performance Evaluation</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2019. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00TRDD.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kenya
Kozhobekova, Aizharkyn. <i>Protect to Prevent: Enabling Central Asians to Protect Religious Freedom as a Preventative Approach to Addressing Violent Extremism</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2022. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Final-Evaluation-Report-Protect-To-Prevent-STD060.pdf .	Multi-methods	Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan
Limange, Joseph, Inna Bagayoko, and Moussa Bagayoko. <i>Rapid Appraisal Report: Effectiveness of the Theory of Change of Appui À La Cohésion Communautaire Et Les Opportunités De Réconciliation Et Développement (ACCORD) Project</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2018. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00T81P.pdf .	Qualitative	Mali
Lumbantoruan, Christina. <i>Building Resilience through Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration to Prevent Violent Extremism in Indonesia</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2022. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Final-Evaluation-Report_STD070.pdf .	Multi-methods	Indonesia
Mahling, Kimberly, Jose Carlos, Assi Kimou, Youssouf Touré, and Isabelle Becho. <i>Cote D'Ivoire Political Transition and Inclusion Program Final Performance Evaluation: An Evaluation for Learning, Evaluation, and Research Activity II</i> . United States Agency for International Development. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00Z3ZVW.pdf .	Qualitative	Côte D'Ivoire

Marou, Garba Zakari. <i>Final Evaluation: Youth, Peace and Security</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2021. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Rapport-evaluation-finale-FRG003-Anglais-VF120222.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Niger
McCallum, Judith. <i>Rift Valley Local Empowerment for Peace II (LEAP II) Final Evaluation Report</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2013. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/pdacy449.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kenya
McCormack, Meghan, Azamat Bakiev, Baktygul Kapalova, and Kyzzybek Nurbekova. <i>End of Project Evaluation Report: Women and Girls as Drivers of Peace and the Prevention of Radicalization</i> . UNFPA, 2019. https://www.un.org/peacebuilding/sites/www.un.org.peacebuilding/files/documents/kyrgyzstan_2018_project_evaluation_2_english_0.pdf .	Multi-methods	Kyrgyzstan
McCormack, Meghan, Baktygul Kapalova, Azamat Bakiev, and Kyzzybek Nurbekova. <i>Post Project Evaluation Report: Women and Girls as Drivers of Peace and the Prevention of Radicalization</i> . UNFPA, 2019. https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5db70e83fc0a966cf4cc42ea/t/65847716ee24634385bd85e8/1703180055194/862.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kyrgyzstan
Monzani, Bernardo, Anthony Sarota, and Sarota Venturi. <i>Inuka! Community-Led Security Approaches to Violent Extremism in Coastal Kenya</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2018. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Final-Evaluation-Inuka-Community-Led-Security-Approaches-to-Violent-Extremism-in-Coastal-Kenya-October-2018.pdf .	Multi-methods	Kenya
NIWETU <i>Endline Evaluation Final Report August 2020</i> . United States Agency for International Development. https://dec.usaid.gov/dec/content/Detail.aspx?vID=47&ctID=ODVhZjk4NWQtM2YyMi00YjRmLTkxNjktZTcxMjM2NDhMjY2Uy&rID=NTc4MDE3 .	Mixed Methods	Kenya
Nuwakora, Cliff Bernard, and Lucie Luguga. <i>Mid-Term Evaluation of the Inclusive Democratic Governance Pillar</i> . United Nations Development Programme, 2019. https://erc.undp.org/evaluation/documents/download/12512 .	Qualitative	Tanzania
Pipe, Roger, Jama Egal, Jane Meme, Lucas Malla, Zamzam Billow, and Aden Abdi. <i>Somalia Program Support Services: Final Performance Evaluation of the Transition Initiatives for Stabilization Project</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2016. https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5db70e83fc0a966cf4cc42ea/t/5f491ed3020a2654cb8d19b7/1598627541959/1344.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Somalia
Retzlaff, Nina, Chinara Esengul, and Paul English. <i>Support to the Prevention of Radicalization to Violence in Prisons and Probation Settings in the Kyrgyz Republic</i> . United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), 2021. https://www.unodc.org/documents/evaluation/Independent_Project_Evaluations/2021/Final_Evaluation_Report_XACZ61.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Kyrgyzstan
Tesfaye, Beza, T. McDougal, B. Maclin, and A. Blum. <i>If Youth Are Given The Chance: Effects of Education and Civic Engagement on Somali Youth Support of Political Violence</i> . Mercy Corps, 2018. https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2019-11/If Youth Are Given the Chance_LR_FINAL.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Somalia
Tesfaye, Beza. <i>Critical Choices: Assessing the Effects of Education and Civic Engagement on Somali Youths' Propensity Towards Violence</i> . Mercy Corps, 2016. https://www.mercycorps.org/sites/default/files/2020-01/CRITICAL_CHOICES_REPORT_FINAL_DIGITAL.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Somaliland

Trujillo, Horacio R. <i>Early Warning/Early Response Mechanisms in Northern Nigeria</i> . Search for Common Ground, 2019. https://www.sfcg.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Final_Evaluation_Early_Warning_Early_Response_Mechanisms_in_Northern_Nigeria_October_2019.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Nigeria
<i>Tunisia Transition Initiative</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2014. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00KI6C.pdf .	Qualitative	Tunisia
<i>USAID'S MYDev Program Final Report 2013-2019</i> . United States Agency for International Development/Education Development Center, 2019. https://www.edc.org/usaid-mydev-program-final-report .	Multi-methods	Philippines
<i>USAID'S MYDev Program Final Report 2013-2019</i> . United States Agency for International Development/Education Development Center, 2019. https://www.edc.org/usaid-mydev-program-final-report .	Quantitative descriptive	Philippines
<i>USAID'S MYDev Program Final Report 2013-2019</i> . United States Agency for International Development/Education Development Center, 2019. https://www.edc.org/usaid-mydev-program-final-report .	Quantitative randomized controlled trials	Philippines
Vittum, Katherine, Otieno Ombok, Kenneth Odary, and Gloria Mmoji. <i>Kenya Tuna Uwezo: Final Performance Evaluation</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2016. https://issuu.com/odary_ken/docs/kenya_tuna_uwezo_final_performance_evaluation/101 .	Qualitative	Kenya
Wood, Sarah, Lucas Malla, Patrick Okwarah, Suleiman Omar, and Mathias Kjaer. <i>Somalia Program Support Services Transition Initiatives fFor Stabilization Plus (Tis+)</i> . United States Agency for International Development, 2019. https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PA00TW4W.pdf .	Mixed Methods	Somalia

